

Heterocyclic Compounds containing Arsenic in the Ring. A Preliminary Note.

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In the domain of organo-arsenic derivatives only a limited number of compounds are either isologous with hetero-nitrogenous ring compounds or in which arsenic takes part in the ring-formation. No compound is known which is isologous with indole. The present investigation was undertaken in November, 1933 with a view to prepare an arsenic analogue of indole. 1-Chloroarsindole was prepared by a direct method and the results of the same together with the procedures to be adopted towards establishing the correctness of the said formula were published (*Proc. Indian Science Congress*, 1933, p. 169). It appears that Mannich (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1935, 273, 275) while studying the action of arsenic trichloride on 1-phenyl-1:3-diethylaminopropine, $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{C} : \text{C} \text{CH}_2\text{N}\cdot\text{Et}_2$ to obtain $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{CCl} : \text{C}(\text{AsCl}_2)\text{CH}_2\text{N}\cdot\text{Et}_2$, analogous to the action of AsCl_3 on $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{C} : \text{CH}$, got unexpectedly two different compounds, viz., (i) $\text{Cl}-\text{As}\cdot\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\cdot\text{CCl} : \text{C}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{NEt}_2$ and

(ii) $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{CCl} : \text{CH}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{NEt}_2$, HCl. The first compound was found to be isologous with indole and was accordingly designated as 2-(diethylaminomethyl)-1:3-dichloroarsindole and second one as the hydrochloride of 1-phenyl-1-chloro-3-diethylaminopropene. The author claims to be the pioneer in the synthesis of arsindole but probably through oversight he had not taken any note of the scheme of arsindole synthesis already published in 1933.

The chloroarsindole has been prepared by the present author by the action of β -chlorovinyl-dichloroarsine on pure benzene in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride as follows:

The formula assigned to chloroarsindole has been proved to be correct by the following syntheses: The experimental details will be communicated shortly.

Compounds of the types $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{CH}=\text{CH})_2\text{Hg}$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{CH}=\text{CH} \cdot \text{HgCl}$ and $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{CH}=\text{CH})_3\text{As}$ have been prepared and attempts are being made to synthesise chloroarsindole from them.